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THE DISTRIBUTION AMONG FOODSTUFFS (ESPECIALLY THOSE SUITABLE FOR THE RATIONING OF ARMIES) OF THE SUBSTANCES REQUIRED FOR THE PREVENTION OF
(A) BERIBERI AND (B) SCURVY.

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NOTE.—This paper has been unavoidably held back. The authors have taken the opportunity to make some additions, *e.g.*, references to the Mesopotamia Commission Report and an Appendix.

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I. INTRODUCTION.

Sufficient evidence is now available to permit beriberi and scurvy to be classed among the "deficiency" diseases due to a defective diet without further comment. The view that scurvy is caused by the absence of fresh food, especially vegetables, was established in popular opinion more than 150 years ago,* and is maintained to-day, in spite of various attempts, some of which are quite recent (*e.g.*, JACKSON and HARLEY, 1900, and COPLANS, 1904), to suggest and defend a different etiology. The study of beriberi is confined to more recent times, and, during the last twenty years, has received the attention of many capable investigators. The researches of EIJKMAN, GRIJNS, BRADDON, and FRASER and STANTON, among others, have proved beriberi among the rice-eating populations of the East Indies, where it is prevalent, to be due to a definite deficiency in the diet of the persons afflicted. The defect was traced to a loss of specially valuable constituents of the rice grain which occurred during milling and polishing after the modern method, and these workers showed that the disease could be prevented if unmilled rice were substituted for milled rice in the diet, or if the bran removed during milling were added to the polished rice. The later workers on this subject include SCHAUMANN (1910) and FUNK (1913), in whose papers a complete bibliography of the subject may be found. To FUNK (1912) we owe the expression "vitamine," which he invented to express the unknown essential principle whose absence from a diet occasions beriberi. The term has, however, become established in general use to signify any accessory substance necessary for satisfactory metabolism, deficiency of which in a diet will lead to the occurrence of a "deficiency" disease.

The present position may be summed up as follows: For perfect nutrition the human being requires—in addition to an adequate ration of fat, protein, carbohydrate, salts and water—a sufficient supply of accessory food factor or vitamines. These substances have not so far been successfully isolated; little is known of their chemical or physical properties, and, at the present time, their presence can only be detected by biological methods. There are, at least, two† distinct classes of these vitamines:

*JAMES LIND. "A Treatise on the Scurvy." 2nd ed. London. 1757.

† Rickets and pellagra, and some less known diseases of cattle, are also generally classed among the diseases due to defective nutrition: investigation in these cases is, however, not nearly so far advanced as in scurvy and beriberi.

(1) the vitamine whose presence in a diet is an essential for the proper nutrition of the nervous system, and whose absence or deficiency will give rise to beriberi—for the sake of brevity this may be called the anti-neuritic or anti-beriberi vitamine, and (2) the anti-scorbutic vitamine, whose absence or deficiency in a diet will occasion scurvy with its characteristic pathological changes.*

Scurvy and beriberi are now known to be respectively caused by a deficiency in these two different classes of vitamine, which possess different properties, play a different part in metabolism, and are differently distributed among food-stuffs in nature.

Deficiency diseases are practically non-existent among modern civilised Europeans, for, when living upon the ordinary mixed diet of civilisation, it is difficult to avoid getting an adequate amount of each separate vitamine. It is where the diet is more simple, as is the case with many Eastern races, that the risk of deficiency disease becomes proportionately greater. The food then needs careful scrutiny to ensure that all necessary vitamines should be included in the comparatively few substances of which the diet is composed.

In the case of Europeans, however, a variety of special causes may lead to what is virtually a restricted diet, *qua* vitamines, although it may not be apparent. Armies on active service, exploration parties in arctic regions, may enjoy a varied supply of preserved and sterilised foods but in effect be deprived of vitamines, these being wholly or in part destroyed by the high temperatures and other processes to which the food has been subjected in the course of preparation. Under such conditions beriberi or scurvy may take some months to develop to an acute stage, but there is little doubt that the defective diet will give rise to a general condition of ill health and inefficiency some time before definite symptoms of these diseases can be diagnosed by the physician. It is clearly of the utmost importance to ensure that a satisfactory diet should be available for soldiers and sailors on active service, more especially when one considers the great strain, both mental and physical,

*The spongy and septic condition of the gums characteristic of scurvy is probably partly, if not wholly, due to secondary bacterial infection. The defences against invasion are well known to be weaker in the mouth than in many other parts of the body, and in scurvy are further reduced owing to the abnormal condition of the blood system. This may account for the view frequently advanced, with some experimental support, that scurvy is an infectious disease of bacterial origin.

to which they are subjected. The first step towards this achievement is to obtain trustworthy information as to the distribution of these essential vitamins in ordinary foodstuffs. Some of this knowledge is already available, and it was with the hope of supplementing the existing data upon the subject that the present work was undertaken.

II. EXPERIMENTAL.

1. DISTRIBUTION OF ANTI-BERIBERI VITAMINE.

The distribution of the anti-beriberi vitamine among various foodstuffs was made the subject of a special investigation by COOPER (1913 and 1914), working in this Institute. We have used his methods, and our endeavour has been to extend his work with special reference to substances which are dry and portable, and hence specially suited to the rationing of troops on active service.

The deficiency polyneuritis of birds (which is readily induced experimentally by a diet of polished rice, see Fig. 1) has been accepted as analogous to human beriberi from the similarity of its etiology, symptoms and method of cure. COOPER chiefly used the pigeon as experimental animal. This bird is specially adapted for the study of the anti-neuritic vitamins, seeing that it is extremely susceptible to polyneuritis, but does not apparently take scurvy, even when deprived of anti-scorbutic material. Our work has also been done with the pigeon, and, following the methods of COOPER, we have studied the anti-neuritic properties of a series of foodstuffs by means of the following two types of experiments:—

A. Preventive Experiments.—In which the aim was to determine the minimum amount of the foodstuff that must be added to a vitamine-free diet to prevent onset of polyneuritis. Polished rice (40 grams daily) formed the vitamine-free diet, and prevention was reckoned to be successfully accomplished if the bird shewed no symptoms after 50-60 days. Unprotected birds usually develop acute polyneuritis after 15-25 days.

B. Curative Experiments.—In which the birds were fed upon polished rice until acute symptoms of polyneuritis were observed. Determination was then made of the minimum amount of the foodstuff in question which would effect a cure when administered by the mouth. Birds suffering from acute polyneuritis will usually die within twenty-four hours if not treated. In order to get the requisite amount of cura-

tive material (anti-beriberi vitamine) absorbed in time, it was frequently necessary to concentrate the vitamine. To do this a weighed quantity of the air-dry material was extracted with alcohol by shaking up with alcohol in the cold for some hours. The alcohol was then evaporated at low temperature under reduced pressure, and the residue was taken up in a small measured quantity of water. Definite amounts of this watery solution formed the curative doses, but in order to obtain a fairer comparison the amount of the dose was reckoned in terms of the original foodstuff.

TABLE I.
PREVENTIVE EXPERIMENTS.

Minimum daily ration which must be added to a diet of polished rice to prevent onset of Polyneuritis (Beriberi) in a pigeon of 300 to 400 grams weight.

SUBSTANCE.	DAILY RATION.		OBSERVER.	NOTES ON RESULTS.
	Natural food-stuff. (Grms.)	Dry Weight. (Grms.)		
Wheat Germ, sample R.I., free from bran ...	1.5	1.3	H.C. & E.M.H.	Complete protection.
Wheat bran, sample R.I., free from germ ...	More than 1.5	More than 1.4	„ „	No protection with 1.5 gms. daily. Polyneuritis occurred in same time as in control birds.
„ „	More than 2.5	More than 2.2	„ „	Small degree of protection. Mean time of onset delayed about two weeks.
Yeast extract, commercial, sample A ...	0.5	0.35	„ „	Protection not secured in all cases.
Pressed yeast ...	1.0	0.7	„ „	Protection.
Barley, unhusked ...	2.5	0.5	COOPER, <i>Journ. Hyg.</i> 1913 and 14	
Lentils ...	—	3.0	„ „	
Barley, husked ...	3.7	3.2	„ „	
Barley, husked ...	5.0	4.5	„ „	
Egg-yolk ...	3	1.5	„ „	
Beef-muscle ...	20	5.0	„ „	
Ox heart-muscle ...	5	1.7	„ „	
Ox brain ...	6	1.2	„ „	
Ox liver ...	3	0.9	„ „	
Sheep brain ...	12	2.5	„ „	
Fish-muscle ...	More than 10	More than 2	„ „	
Cheese ...	More than 8	More than 5.6	„ „	Protection not secured with these amounts.
Cow's milk ...	„ „ .35	„ „ 3.5	„ „	

TABLE II.

CURATIVE EXPERIMENTS.

Minimum amounts of foodstuffs required to cure Polyneuritis (Beriberi) in a pigeon 300 to 400 grams weight. The doses are reckoned in terms of the original foodstuffs.

SUBSTANCE.	Preparation of curative material.	Amount of dose given.		RESULT.	OBSERVER.
		In terms of the natural foodstuff.	In terms of dry weight 100-110° C.		
Wheat germ— Commercial sample, cooked ...	Extracted with alcohol ...	grams.	grams.	Improvement ... Sometimes cures Cure ...	H.C. & E.M.H.
Sample A "picked," uncooked		8 12 16	6.9 10.3 13.8		
Sample B "picked," uncooked	Unextracted ...	10 15	8.7 13.0	Incomplete cure Complete cure Sometimes cures Cure ...	" "
*Maize germ ...		1.0 2.5	0.9 2.2		
*Rice germ ...	Unextracted ...	1.0 to 3.0 0.5 to 1.0	— —	Cure ... Cure ...	" "
Wheat bran— Stone ground, not free from germ.	Unextracted ..	5.0	—	Sometimes cures No cure ...	" "
Roller milled, free from germ...	Unextracted ...	3.0 5.0	— —	Sometimes cures No cure ...	" "
Rice bran, containing germ ...	Unextracted ...	6.0 10.0	— —	No cure ... Complete cure ...	" "
Turbot fish-roe (hard) ...	Extracted with alcohol ...	35 70 140	10 20 40	Cure almost comp Cure complete ... Cure complete ...	" "
Egg-yolk ...		60=4 yolks	30		
Dried whole egg, com'l, samp. I.	Given without extraction ...	40=abt. 4 "	38	Cure ...	COOPER, 1913.
" " " " II.	Do.	30= " 3 "	29	Cure ...	H.C. & E.M.H.
" " " " II.	Do.	20= " 2 "	—	Cure ...	" "
Malt Extract— 1st sample ...	Given without extraction ...	5	4.2	Cure ...	COOPER, 1914, I.
2nd sample ...		7	5.1	Cure ...	
3rd sample ...		10	9.2	No Cure ...	
Meat extract, com'l, sample I.	Do.	3	2.8	No improvement, bird died ...	H.C. & E.M.H.
" " " " II.	Do.	6.5	5.2	No improvement, bird died ...	
Raw beef ...	Extracted with alcohol ...	140	30 approx. 106	Cure ... Cure incomplete	COOPER, 1913. H.C. & E.M.H.
"Maconochie" ration ...		Do.			
"New ration" roast beef tinned, submitted for examination by the Dept. of Hygiene, R.A.M. College, on 19th June, 1916 ...	Do.	350	112	Very slight im- provem't, no cure	" "

* Picked out from the un-milled grain by hand in the laboratory.

TABLE II.—*continued.*

CURATIVE EXPERIMENTS—*continued.*

Minimum amounts of foodstuffs required to cure Polyneuritis (Beriberi) in a pigeon 300 to 400 grams weight. The doses are reckoned in terms of the original foodstuffs.

SUBSTANCE.	Preparation of curative material.	Amount of dose given.		RESULT.	OBSERVER.	
		In terms of the natural foodstuff.	In terms of dry weight 100–110° C.			
Dried peas... ..	Extracted with alcohol ...	30	26	Incomplete cure	" "	
" "		40	35	Complete cure ...		
" "	Unextracted ...	10	9	Cure	" "	
Pea flour, kilned		Extracted with alcohol ...	80	—		Slight impr'vm't, No cure ...
Dried lentils	Do.	20	18	Cure	COOPER, 1913. H.C. & E.M.H.	
Dried vegetables, commercial } Sample "Spring greens" }	Do.	40	35	Cure		
	Do.	120	105	Complete cure ...		
Potatoes, peelings	Do.	180	36	Died	" "	
" "	Do.	630	126	Improvement, no cure		
Potatoes, insides... ..	Do.	200	40	Incomplete cure	" "	
" "	Do.	350	70	Cure		
Pressed yeast	Autolysed ...	2.0	0.4	Cured slowly ...	" " COOPER, 1914, II. H.C. & E.M.H.	
" "	Do.	3.0 to 6.0	0.6 to 1.2	Cure		
Yeast extract, com'l, Sample A	Given without extraction ...	1.5 to 2.0	1.0 to 1.3	Complete cure ...		
Dried fruits, currant	Extracted with alcohol ...	60	47	No improvement	" " " " " " " "	
" " "		Do.	19	16		No improvement
" " dates		Do.	26	21		Slight improv't, death delayed
" " "		Do.	26	21		Slight temporary improvement ...
Proprietary article, dry powder, stated to contain vitamins in a concentrated form ...	Given without extraction ...	12 31		No improv't., died Temp. improve- ment, no cure	" " " "	

In case of cereals and some other materials rich in anti-neuritic vitamine, we gave the curative dose of the original foodstuff without preliminary extraction. By this means we avoided the loss of vitamine due to the process of extraction. This loss was very considerable; see, for example, the case of dry peas given in Table II., where the curative dose

of unextracted material was 10 grams, but that estimated from experiments made with an extract was as high as 40 grams. The original material was administered, without extraction, whenever possible, in order to obtain a better absolute value for the vitamine-content of the foodstuff in the natural condition. The drawback of this method is that absorption is slower and one does not get the swift dramatic cures commonly obtained when the curative principle is given in a soluble form. But if care is taken to see that the animal's crop is empty before administering a cure, digestion will not be too slow to permit of sufficient vitamine being absorbed in time to save the bird.

There is no doubt that the most trustworthy results are obtained from the preventive tests. They are, however, very exacting and laborious, the feeding is artificial, and must be continued for about two months, with daily careful supervision. If the enquiry were limited to this type of experiment its scope would be seriously restricted. In considering the values obtained from curative experiments, allowance must be made for a large margin of error, seeing that it is impossible to control the onset of polyneuritis so that the type of symptom and the severity of the condition should always be the same at the time of administration of the cure.

The principal data obtained are set forth in Tables I. and II., in which also many of the results of COOPER (*loc. cit.*) are included for the sake of completeness. Some of the results given in these Tables were anticipated by the workers mentioned on page 150, but COOPER was the first to make a systematic attempt to obtain a comparative set of values for the different foodstuffs as regards ability to prevent beriberi.

From Tables I. and II. it is seen that the anti-beriberi vitamine is extremely widespread, and is found present to a greater or less degree in almost every natural foodstuff investigated. The principal sources of this vitamine, however, are at once seen to be in the seeds of plants or the eggs of animals, where it is probably stored* as a provision for the nutrition of the offspring during the early period of its existence.

From the practical point of view, the most important result is the fact that *one of the chief sources of the anti-beriberi vitamine should be in the seeds of plants, including, as this does, the cereals and edible pulses.* The

* It is interesting in this connection to note that among a population upon the verge of beriberi owing to a defective diet, it is frequently the pregnant women who are the first to shew acute symptoms (see VEDDER. "Beriberi." London. 1913. p. 61).

FIG. 1.

Shewing the various stages in Milling of the Rice Grain.

- I. Rice grain in the natural condition, retaining the husk or enclosing glumes.
- II. After removal of the husk, but retaining the pericarp or "silver-skin," and the embryo, which is shaded.
- III. After milling and polishing; both "silver-skin" and embryo are removed and the grains are then "polished" by rubbing with talc between sheepskins.

FIG. 2.*

Diagram of a longitudinal section through a grain of wheat, shewing

B Pericarp, forming the branny envelope.

A Aleurone layer of cells forming the outermost layer of the endosperm removed with the pericarp during milling.

E Parenchymatous cells of the endosperm.

G Embryo or germ.

*Reproduced, with the permission of the Controller of H.M. Stationery Office, from Figs. 1 and 2 in Dr. J. M. HAMILL'S "Report to the Local Government Board on the nutritive value of bread made from different varieties of wheat flour," 1911.

FIG. 3.*

Cross section through the branny envelope and outer portion of the endosperm of wheat grain, shewing—*P*, the pericarp; *E*, endosperm, consisting of *a*, layer of aleurone cells and *p*, parenchymatous cells.

*Reproduced, with the permission of the Controller of H.M. Stationery Office, from Figs. 1 and 2 in Dr. J. M. HAMILL'S "Report to the Local Government Board on the nutritive value of bread made from different varieties of wheat flour," 1911.

great value of certain beans (*e.g.*, KATJANGIDJO, *Phaseolus radiatus*) in the prevention and cure of both avian polyneuritis and human beriberi, has been repeatedly shewn by GRIJNS (1901) and the other Dutch observers. In the case of cereals* an interesting differentiation exists in the different parts of the seed (see Figs. 1, 2 and 3). The largest deposit of the vitamine is present in the *embryo* or germ, while the bran (pericarp + *aleurone layer*) comes second in order of importance. The *endosperm* (especially when deprived of the *aleurone layer*, which is included in the bran in modern milling) is deficient in anti-neuritic vitamine, and will cause beriberi if employed as sole diet. One well-known example of a cereal endosperm is polished rice (see Fig. 1), where the germ is removed with bran during the milling and polishing. Another is ordinary white wheaten flour, in the preparation of which a similar deprivation takes place in the modern roller mills. In this case, during the "break" on the rollers, the oily germ is squeezed out flat, and subsequently can be separated completely from the flour and the bran. Both white flour and polished rice produce polyneuritis in pigeons in an exactly similar way, and, if the less complete evidence available in case of rye and maize be also taken into account, there is no doubt a general rule

*A more detailed account of our experiments with cereals is published in the *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1917, read February 15th, 1917 (in the press),

that among cereals the anti-neuritic vitamine is concentrated in the germ.

The potency of the cereal embryo in the cure of polyneuritis is very great. In case of wheat germ, 2.5 grams usually (and rarely 1.0 gram) sufficed to cure a pigeon of 300-400 grams' weight in an acutely ill condition. In case of rice embryo, cures were obtained with amounts varying from 0.5 gram to 1.0 gram.

The prevailing opinion, hitherto, has been that the substance preventing beriberi was situated in the cuticle of the husked grain, in the layer of cells (*aleurone layer*) immediately below the pericarp (see Fig. 3). This view is based upon the well-known influence of decorticated rice in inducing human beriberi, and the prevention and cure of the disease by the addition of rice polishings and their extracts. The true explanation lies in the fact that in the milling and polishing of rice the germ is removed with the bran (see Fig. 1). On comparing the values of (1) commercial rice bran and (2) the pure germ, separated from the grain by hand in the laboratory, we found the latter ten times as potent as the former for the cure of pigeon polyneuritis.

An interesting analogy with the seeds and embryos of plants is offered by the eggs of birds and fishes, which also form valuable sources of anti-beriberi vitamine. The successful cures obtained with desiccated eggs shew the great resistance offered by this vitamine to drying.

Yeast is another substance rich in anti-neuritic properties, which it retains even after extraction or autolysis. Yeast was the only unicellular organism investigated, and it may be significant of the universality of this vitamine that it should be abundantly present in this instance.

Milk, cheese and potatoes appear to be among the least valuable foods from this point of view; other vegetables and meat contain a moderate amount of anti-beriberi vitamine, but are very inferior when compared with eggs or the seeds of plants.

2. DISTRIBUTION OF ANTI-SCORBUTIC VITAMINE.

While there is a good deal of empirical knowledge upon this subject, few accurate scientific data are available, and what exist are found chiefly in the work of AXEL HOLST and his colleagues Drs. FÜRST and FRÖLICH, in the University of Christiania (1907, 1912, 1913). By depriving guinea-

pigs of fresh green food, and offering only a diet of grain and water, these workers were able to induce a disease analogous to human scurvy, from which the animal died within a month from the commencement of the restricted diet. The post-mortem appearances shewed all the lesions of typical scurvy, and included changes in bone, cartilage and bone marrow, loosening of the teeth, and, in addition, hæmorrhages, which might occur in any situation. These workers also studied the influence of various additions to this scurvy diet, and investigated the distribution of the anti-scorbutic principle among various vegetable foodstuffs and its resistance to drying and to exposure to high temperatures. The commonly accepted view that fresh vegetables and fruits are the chief source of anti-scorbutic vitamine was abundantly confirmed by their experimental work.

No symptoms suggesting beriberi were detected, nor were any nerve lesions discovered in these experimental animals, whose scurvy diet of various grains and water included unmilled cereals and contained abundant anti-neuritic vitamine. In any circumstances, the guinea-pig appears to be so highly susceptible to scurvy that attempts to produce beriberi have not been successful. The distribution of the anti-beriberi vitamine is very widespread, and on any diet adapted to this animal it seems impossible to protect satisfactorily from scurvy without at the same time supplying a sufficiency of the anti-neuritic substance. For this reason the guinea-pig is as admirably adapted for the study of scurvy as is the pigeon for that of beriberi.

During the last few months we have extended the work of HOLST and his colleagues in the direction of foodstuffs which are portable and convenient for transport, and hence suited for the rationing of armies. The methods we have followed have, in principle, been those of the Norwegian workers. The principal modification has been the addition of milk, subjected to prolonged heating at a high temperature (120° C. for one hour), to the scurvy diet of grain and water. By this addition we have not been able to detect any appreciable change in the special symptoms of the disease or time of onset; but the general condition of the animal is much improved, apart from the scurvy, and the influence of the inclusion of the anti-scorbutic substances can be studied with less complication from such factors as mere inanition and starvation (see Table III., and compare curves A and B in Fig. 4).

FIG. 4.

Weight Charts of five typical experiments shewing the anti-scorbutic value of orange juice and fresh cabbage leaves.

CURVE A. Typical scurvy on a diet of oats, bran and water.

CURVE B. Typical scurvy on a diet of oats, bran and sterilised milk (heated to 120° C. for 1 hour in the autoclave).

CURVE C. Typical scurvy on a diet of oats, bran and water, cured by addition of orange juice and autoclaved milk to the diet on the 22nd day, when the symptoms were well marked.

CURVE D. Weight chart shewing influence of 5 c.c. fresh orange juice daily added to the "scurvy" diet; autoclaved milk added to the diet on the 56th day.

CURVE E. Normal weight chart on a diet of oats, bran and cabbage leaves (30 grams daily).

CURVE F. Weight chart on diet of oats, bran, autoclaved milk and 3 c.c. fresh orange juice daily; specially favourable circumstances—warm weather, etc.

condition when autoclaved milk is substituted for water in the diet, although the course of the scurvy is not modified. Weight is better maintained throughout, and, at the beginning of the experiment, some growth takes place.

Experiment III. (Curve C, Fig. 4) deals with a successful cure from scurvy by means of fresh orange juice. The first part of the experiment, on a diet of oats, bran and water, reproduces Experiment I. very closely. On the 22nd day, when the guinea-pig is losing weight rapidly and shews acutely sore joints, orange juice (10 c.c. daily) is added to the diet, and 50-60 grams of autoclaved milk. Little improvement is seen for four or five days, and the fall in weight continues. After this, however, a gradual improvement takes place, but it is 6-7 weeks after the beginning of the "cure" before the animal may be considered normal. The soreness of the joints persists long after the general health and weight have been restored.

The Curves D, E, and F, Fig. 4, shew the weight curves on diets which give adequate protection from scurvy, and are included for purposes of comparison. Curve E shews the increase of weight upon a normal diet of oats, bran and cabbage leaves (30 grams daily); and Curves D and F shew the result of substituting fresh orange juice for the cabbage leaves, with the addition also of autoclaved milk.

TABLE III.

EXPERIMENT I. (Guinea-pig 47). Diet: Oats, Bran and Water *ad lib.*
(see Curve A, Fig. 4).

Date.	No. of days from beginning of Experiment.	Condition of the Animal.	Weight (Grams).	Amount of oats and bran eaten daily, average (Grams).
29-11-16	0		280	(21 days) 34.
16-12-16	17	Leg joints tender	290	
20-12-16	21		280	
25-12-16	26	Leg joints tender, incisor teeth loose	240	(9 days) 14.
29-12-16	30	Died	185	

EXPERIMENT II. (Guinea-pig 49). Diet: Oats, Bran and Autoclaved Milk (1 hour at 120° C.) *ad lib.* (see Curve B, Fig 4).

29-11-16	0		290	(17 days) 25.
15-12-16	16	One leg joint tender	350	
25-12-16	26	Teeth loose	240	
27-12-16	28	Died	230	(12 days) 5.

TABLE III.—*continued.*

EXPERIMENT III. (Guinea-pig 58). Diet: Oats, Bran and Water *ad lib.* for 22 days, with production of acute Scurvy; followed by the addition of Orange Juice, 10 c.c. daily, and Autoclaved Milk, about 50 grams daily, leading to a satisfactory cure (see Curve C, Fig. 4).

Date.	No of days from beginning of Experiment.	Condition of the Animal.	Weight (Grams).	Amount of oats and bran eaten daily average (Grams).
6-12-16	0		320	
16-12-16	10	One leg sore "Scurvy position" noticed, the sore hind-leg is raised in the air while the animal lies down on the other three legs.	315	(18 days) 33.
22-12-16	16		320	
24-12-16	18		Great fall in weight begins	
28-12-16	22	Animal very weak <i>Cure started</i> , 10 c.c. fresh orange juice + 50-60 grms. autoclaved milk daily added to oats & bran diet	250	(5 days) 10.
29-12-16	23	Condition very bad	235	(10 days) 15.
1-1-17	26	Still very sore	235	
3-1-17	28	Lying in "Scurvy position"	270	
5-1-17	31	Soreness of joints improved	290	
7-1-17	33		295	(41 days) 45.
13-1-17	39	General condition good—joints still sore	325	
24-1-17	50	Ditto	365	
13-2-17	60	Soreness much improved	460	
21-2-17	68	No symptoms	482	
27-2-17	74	Excellent health, no symptoms	540	

It will be gathered that these experiments are laborious and tedious. The guinea-pigs in most cases require a certain amount of hand feeding to gain assurance that the requisite doses of the materials studied are really taken, and much care is also needed to render the foodstuffs palatable, for many of those studied are far removed from the natural food of this animal, and different treatment is required in each separate case. Further, a good deal of skilled attention is necessary if the general health and weight of the animal are to be maintained, apart from the question of scurvy. Under these circumstances the output of work possible from any one worker is limited, and we have been fortunate in obtaining the assistance of the following workers to whom, in conjunction with ourselves, the investigation of the following foodstuffs has been entrusted:—

Miss RUTH SKELTON (fresh and dried vegetables and lime juice).

Dr. E. MARION DELF and Miss OLIVE LODGE (fresh fruit juices; pulses, soaked and germinated).

Our endeavour is to obtain accurate quantitative figures expressing the relative anti-scorbutic value of a large range of different foodstuffs. The work is at present incomplete, but enough information is available from our own results and those of the Norwegian workers (confirmed throughout by our own) to construct the following Table IV., in which a rough estimate is given of the comparative value of the various substances in the prevention of (a) beriberi and (b) scurvy.

TABLE IV.
VALUE OF FOODSTUFFS AS PREVENTIVE AGAINST SCURVY AND BERIBERI.

Foodstuffs.	Water content per cent. (Approx.)	Value against Beriberi.	Value against Scurvy.
CEREALS—			
Whole grain, wheat	10 to 13	+	0
Endosperm, polished rice		0	0
" " white flour (wheat)			
Bran, e.g., rice		+	0
" " wheat		+	0
Germ or embryo, e.g., rice		+	0
" " " wheat		+	0
PULSES—			
Whole, in dry condition	12	+	0
GERMINATED PULSES (or Cereals)...	50	+	+
VEGETABLES—			
Potatoes	80	0	+
Fresh, e.g., cabbage	90	+	+
" " onions			+
" " carrot			+
Desiccated vegetables	10 to 15	+	+
Pickled, e.g., cabbage	—	—	0
FRUIT JUICE—			
Fresh, e.g. orange	90	—	+
" " lemon			+
EGGS—			
Fresh	70	+	—
Desiccated	6	+	0
MEAT—			
Fresh	70	+	+
Tinned			0
MILK—			
Cow's, fresh	87	0	+
YEAST—			
Pressed, autolysed	77	+	0
Extract, commercial sample A ...	30	+	0

— Signifies not investigated.

It is at once evident that the distribution of the anti-scurvy vitamine is much more restricted than that of the anti-beriberi vitamine. There are here no special places where deposits are found of highly concentrated anti-scorbutic material, but it is present in all living (actively metabolic) tissues of plants and (to a much less degree) in those of animals.

The anti-scorbutic principle has not been found present in dried vegetables or in any dried seeds, such as cereals or pulses, diets of which form the classic means of producing the disease of scurvy. If, however, *these seeds are moistened and allowed to germinate, the anti-scorbutic principle is created anew with the beginnings of active cell life.* As far as our present knowledge goes, the presence of the anti-scorbutic vitamine is always associated with living tissues in which active metabolism is taking place. When viable seeds are in the dry, resting condition, all the *active* processes concerned with life and metabolism are temporarily suspended, and a disappearance of the anti-scorbutic principle accompanies this cessation. If the seed is moistened, rapid

FIG. 5.

Pulses in the dry condition (natural size): a, Peas (*Pisum sativum*); b, Lentils (*Lens esculenta*).

FIG. 6.

Same pulses, as in Fig. 5, after soaking in water for 24 hours and germination for 48 hours, at laboratory temperature (natural size): a, Peas (*Pisum sativum*); b, Lentils (*Lens esculenta*).

absorption of water takes place, the cells once more become turgid and the active processes associated with germination and growth will begin within a few hours. Accompanying this new activity the anti-scorbutic vitamine makes its appearance in the tissues and gradually increases in amount.

These facts were first discovered by FÜRST (1912), and have been amply confirmed by ourselves and our colleagues in an extensive set of experiments with peas (*Pisum sativum*) and lentils (*Lens esculenta*), see Fig. 5. Our method has been to soak these seeds in water for 24 hours, during which time they absorb their own weight of water. They are then loosely packed in a glass funnel and maintained in a moist atmosphere for 1-2 days longer, care been taken to ensure abundant access of air. After 48 hours at laboratory temperature (50-60 F.) the radicle is usually from 0.5 to 1.0 c.m. in length (see Fig. 6), and at this stage we have used the germinated seeds in our experimental diets. Our work is not yet sufficiently advanced to permit of a final statement of the anti-scorbutic value of these germinated pulses in terms of fresh vegetables, but we have obtained complete protection from scurvy with a daily ration of 5 grams, which indicates a vitamine-content comparable with that, for example, of fresh cabbage leaves.

Fruit Juice.—Fresh fruit juices are exceedingly rich in anti-scorbutic vitamine. HOLST and his co-workers pointed out the value of fresh lemon and fresh raspberry juice in preventing experimental scurvy, and our researches have been made chiefly with orange and lemon juice. With these latter we have also been able to effect satisfactory cures from an acute scorbutic condition.

The results of our experiments with preserved fruit juice, *e.g.*, lime juice, have not been so encouraging, the anti-scorbutic power being very feeble in comparison with fresh juices. We are now investigating various methods of preservation in the hope that we may be able to suggest improvements. After reading the history of our Navy and Mercantile Marine, it is impossible to resist the conviction that, in former times, preserved fruit juice was of distinct value in preventing human scurvy, and it is not unlikely that modern methods of manufacture may have introduced some modification detrimental to the anti-scorbutic principle it originally contained.

Fresh Vegetables.—Among the fresh vegetables investigated, the cabbage was found best, partly, no doubt, because fresh green leaves happen to be the natural food of our experimental animal. Onions were also found to be powerfully anti-scorbutic, in spite of their dry appearance from the outside. Ordinary Spanish onions contain 95 per cent. of water, the cells are all in a turgid condition, and, botanically, the vegetable is to be regarded as a live bud. Potatoes and carrots must also be regarded as composed of live turgid tissue; they are also of great value, though found to be slightly inferior to cabbage leaves. In our experiments the potatoes were boiled before giving to the animals, and doubtless there was some loss of the anti-scorbutic principle during the process of cooking. It was, however, a necessary measure, as guinea-pigs are not able to take potatoes in the raw condition.

Milk.—Cow's milk possesses very low anti-scorbutic value. In our experience a ration of 50 grams daily was insufficient to protect guinea-pigs from scurvy. FRÖLICH (1912), however, found that they could be protected by an exclusive diet of milk, and we have found the same result if a minimum of 100 grams is taken daily. This is about twenty times the necessary daily ration (viz., 5 grams) of fresh cabbage or germinated peas, or fresh fruit juice. It seems probable that infants nourished on cow's milk do not obtain any excess of anti-scorbutic principle, especially if the milk is previously boiled. The modern custom of adding a small daily ration of fresh fruit juice, or other anti-scorbutic, appears to have sound and scientific foundation.

Meat.—It is practical experience, obtained especially from the history of Arctic exploration, that fresh meat will prevent human scurvy if taken regularly in fair quantity. The expressed juice of raw meat is also considered to be of value in the cure and prevention of infantile scurvy. For prevention of experimental guinea-pig scurvy, meat was found to be very disappointing, for little, if any, protection could be demonstrated. It must be remembered that meat is an unnatural food for guinea-pigs; they will not eat it even when cooked, and the experiments have to be made with the expressed juices. Allowance must also be made for the high susceptibility to scurvy of this animal, which is undoubtedly much greater than that of the human being; but, when all this is taken into account, one is forced to conclude that meat is far inferior as an anti-scorbutic to vegetables and fruit, and that the daily allowance must

be large if reliance is to be placed upon it for the prevention of scurvy (see also below, p. 171).

Yeast.—Yeast Extract A and autolysed yeast, both of which were shewn to contain the anti-beriberi vitamine in high concentration, uninjured by the process of preparation, were found useless for the prevention of scurvy. Animals receiving as large a daily ration as could conveniently be taken, died of acute scurvy in the same period as the control animals on the "scurvy diet."

RESISTANCE OF THE ANTI-BERIBERI AND ANTI-SCORBUTIC VITAMINE
RESPECTIVELY WHEN EXPOSED TO DRYING, HIGH TEMPERATURES, ETC.

(A) *Drying.*—From the common presence of the anti-beriberi vitamine among dry foodstuffs, it is evident that this substance is not sensitive to the process of drying. It is very significant that its chief sources should be found in dry seeds, such as cereals and pulses.

The case is otherwise with the anti-scorbutic vitamine. This principle seems to be *absent or deficient in all dry foodstuffs*, such, for example, as cereals and pulses, and to be rapidly destroyed when the animal and vegetable tissues, in which it is naturally contained, are subjected to drying. HOLST and FRÖLICH (*loc. cit.*) found dried vegetables of little use for the protection of guinea-pigs from scurvy, and we have confirmed their observations. A similar result has been noted in human experience. Dried vegetables were found useless in the epidemic of scurvy which ravaged the Austrian army in Hungary in the early part of the 18th century (BUDD, 1840), and, including dried potatoes, were tried with the same disappointing results during the American Civil War ("Medical History of the War of Rebellion," Vol. III., Washington).

The temperature at which the tissues are dried seems to be a matter of indifference. In HOLST and FRÖLICH'S experimental work (1912) low temperatures were employed, not exceeding 37° C. The destruction of the anti-scorbutic principle during and after drying, appears to be a gradual process of spontaneous decomposition, which follows disorganisation of the living cells in association with which it is produced. If the tissues are rapidly brought to an absolutely dry condition, this process of destruction is checked and the anti-scorbutic properties are preserved to

a much greater degree (see HOLST and FRÖLICH, 1913). In a similar way these workers found that the expressed juices of acid fruits shewed more stability in respect of their anti-scorbutic value than those of fresh vegetables, and concluded that the rate of this spontaneous decomposition of the vitamine was slowed by the presence of an acid medium. This affords some scientific foundation for the general belief that preserved fruit juices may be relied upon to retain some, at least, of their original anti-scorbutic value.

(B) *High Temperatures.*—There are many isolated observations upon the influence of exposure to high temperatures upon the anti-beriberi vitamine, but no one hitherto has attempted any systematic study of this point. GRIJNS (1901) found that 1-2 hours' exposure to 120° C. destroyed the protective powers of unmilled rice, Katjangidjo beans (*Phaseolus radiatus*), and buffalo meat against avian polyneuritis. EIJKMAN (1906) and SCHAUMANN (1910) confirmed GRIJNS' results on the whole, though the former observer found a greater resistance present in the case of horseflesh. HOLST (1907) detected no particular loss of anti-neuritic vitamine after exposure of dried peas and unpeeled barley to 115° C. for half an hour, but some damage in case of beef after half an hour at 110° C. Most observers have failed to find any significant destruction of this vitamine at 100° C.

The discrepancy between the results of these various experiments is to be explained partly by the roughness of the biological test for the presence of the vitamine in question. It is also partly due to the fact that certain substances originally containing a low concentration of this vitamine (*e.g.*, meat) may be unable to protect from or cure polyneuritis after a certain degree of exposure to high temperatures, whereas others originally richer in this material (*e.g.*, pulses, cereals, etc.) may, after a similar exposure, yet retain a sufficient amount to afford satisfactory protection or cure. Another point to be considered in these experiments is that the temperatures noted appear to be those registered by the autoclave or steamer in which the heating was done, and that no measurements are recorded of the temperatures in the interior of the substances heated. This is an important point, as the latter temperatures remain for a long time below the former, the degree of difference depending on the conductivity of the material heated, and will vary with every type of substance investigated. It therefore seemed to us worth while to make a

series of systematic experiments on this point, and a brief résumé of the results obtained* is set forth in Table V.

Two substances were chosen for the investigation, both rich in anti-beriberi vitamine, viz. (a) the germ (*embryo*) of wheat, and (b) yeast Extract A.

TABLE V.

INFLUENCE OF EXPOSURE to high temperatures upon the anti-beriberi vitamine contained (a) in Wheat Embryo and (b) in Yeast Extract.

SUBSTANCE	Temperature. °C.	Time. Min.	Minimum amount required to cure a pigeon (300 to 400 grms.) suffering from acute Polyneuritis. (Grams).
Wheat embryo— Water content, 11 to 14 %...	unheated 98 to 103	Control 120	1.0 to 2.5 2.5
" " " "	100 to 117	40	5.0
" " " "	118 to 124	120	10.0, did not cure
Yeast extract, A— Water content, 30 % ...	unheated 100	Control 60	1.5 to 2.0 2.0 to 3.0
" " " "	122	60	2.5 to 3.0
" " " "	122	120	about 5.

The data in columns 2 and 3, as to the temperatures reached and the times of exposure, refer to the internal temperatures of the material heated, and were compiled in accordance with the results of a special set of control experiments made for the purpose. The vitamine content of the different samples was estimated by determining the minimum amount necessary to cure acute polyneuritis of pigeons, brought on by an exclusive diet of polished rice. The results in Table V. shew that the anti-neuritic properties of wheat-germ and yeast extract are only slowly impaired by prolonged heating at or near 100° C., but that destruction is much more rapid at temperatures in the neighbourhood of 120° C.

The experiments at 100° C. were devised to be comparable with the ordinary processes of cooking, while those at temperatures from 110° C. to 120° C. were arranged to throw light upon the probable fate of anti-neuritic (anti-beriberi) vitamines during the sterilisation of tinned foods,

* This work is given in detail with full protocols of the individual experiments in a special communication upon the subject—see *Proc. Roy. Soc., B*, 1917, read February 15th, 1917 (in the press).

such as tinned meat, etc. In this connection it is interesting to compare the curative values given in Table II. of—

(a) Raw beef, where the curative dose was an extract equivalent to 30 grams dry weight of the original, and

(b) "Maconachie" ration and "New Army" ration, where an "incomplete cure" and "no cure" were obtained with extracts equivalent to 106 and 112 grams dry weight, respectively.

The destructive influence of high temperatures upon the anti-beriberi vitamine is also seen by noting the superior curative properties of dried peas (unheated) compared with "kilned" pea flour.*

As was the case in exposure to drying, so in exposure to high temperatures, the anti-scorbutic vitamine appears to be much more unstable than the anti-beriberi vitamine. There exists no systematic experimental work upon this point, and we are now starting a series of experiments with the hope of filling the gap. There are, however, some valuable observations of HOLST and FRÖLICH (1912), all of which point to the great sensitiveness of this vitamine to high temperatures. When cabbage leaves were boiled at 100° C., the results obtained indicate that at least one half its anti-scorbutic value was lost in 30 to 60 minutes, and after heating to 120° C. for 60 minutes almost *all* power of protection against scurvy was destroyed (*loc. cit.* Table IV., B p. 70).

In the light of these results it is not to be expected that the anti-scorbutic vitamine will survive the heating to which tinned foods are subjected in order to render them sterile.

III. PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL WORK TO THE PREVENTION, RESPECTIVELY, OF HUMAN BERIBERI, AND HUMAN SCURVY.

The practical use that can be made of these investigations on the distribution of the two classes of essential vitamines will depend on the identity of avian polyneuritis and human beriberi on the one hand, and of guinea-pig scurvy and human scurvy on the other. As regards etiology, nature of symptoms and method of cure, the analogy in both

* This fact needs emphasis, since many samples of pea flour on the market are kilned in the process of preparation, although no mention of this fact is made on the wrapper, etc.

cases is so perfect that they can be considered as physiological equivalents, and the information thus acquired can be applied forthwith.

There is, however, in addition, a great deal of direct evidence to be extracted from human experience. The individual instances may not seem to be altogether conclusive, but when taken together they form a mass of evidence which is very impressive, and afford a striking confirmation of the results obtained from experimental work. To exhaust these instances would need a very long communication. We propose, however, to describe briefly a few cases which seem to us among the more instructive.

PREVENTION OF BERIBERI.

Importance of the nature of the Cereal food in the prevention of human beriberi.—In almost all cases human beriberi is to be attributed to a defect in character of the cereal employed in the diet.

The best known and best studied case is that of the rice-eating populations of the Dutch Indies, Malay States, the Philippine Islands, etc. : it has been the subject of numerous series of researches, among which those of ELJKMAN, GRIJNS, BRADDON, FRASER and STANTON, VEDDER and CHAMBERLAIN are among the more important. All these workers are agreed that the disease is caused by a defect in the rice taken, which defect can be traced to the complete decortication which takes place in the modern steam-milling of the grain. Beriberi is prevented in cases where unmilled rice is substituted for the "polished" rice, or where the bran ("polishings") removed in the milling is added to it. The general opinion is that the anti-beriberi vitamine is contained in the inmost layer of cells (*aleurone layer*) of the skin, which layer of cells is removed with the bran in the process of preparation. Our experiments indicate that the *germ (or embryo) of the grain, also removed during milling, is the principle source of the anti-neuritis vitamine*, present also to a less extent in the bran (see Table II.). It is not so generally realised, however, that the same principle applies to other cereals, or that an equal danger of beriberi is to be apprehended for a wheat-eating population under certain circumstances. In the modern "roller"-milling of wheat, there is complete separation of bran and germ from the flour : unless, therefore, these constituents are purposely included later (as in brown flour, and "standard" flour) one may regard ordinary white flour

and the bread or biscuit baked from it, as being free from these valuable constituents

The deficiency of anti-neuritic vitamine in white wheaten flour was shewn by HOLST (1907), EDIE and SIMPSON (1911) and also by ourselves (see footnote page 150), to occasion polyneuritis in pigeons in a manner exactly similar to polished rice. The following three incidents shew that these results are also applicable to the case of beriberi in man. Under ordinary circumstances this deficiency of vitamine in white bread is well supplied in the other articles of the usual mixed diet of the European. It is in cases where extremes of climate restrict the variety of available foodstuffs, or where there is temporary separation from fresh food supplies on long sea voyages, or by the exigencies of active service on long campaigns, that this defect in the bread ration may become apparent in a tragic manner.

(1) LITTLE (1912) states that in Newfoundland and Labrador, where in mid-winter and spring many persons are obliged to subsist largely on bread, beriberi frequently occurs. At the present time the bread is made from fine wheat flour; in the memory of the older inhabitants, when the bread was made from "brown" flour, the disease was unknown. In 1910 the following interesting event took place:—A ship laden with whole-wheat flour ran ashore, and a considerable proportion of her cargo was removed in order to lighten her, and later was consumed by the adjacent population. There was no case of beriberi in that region for a year following this occurrence.

(2) Beriberi was rare on Norwegian ships before 1894, after which date it became much more frequent. This frequency coincided with an alteration of diet which was made compulsory in that year in response to a popular demand for an "amelioration" of the conditions of life in the Norwegian mercantile marine. Previously the sailors on long voyages used biscuit made from rye flour; subsequently the masters of ships were obliged to supply bread baked from white wheaten flour, or a mixture of wheat and rye flour (HOLST, 1911). It is an interesting corollary upon our own experimental work to note that *in the milling of rye flour there is no separation of the germ.*

(3) The most impressive case of all is to be found in the tragic experiences of our own troops recently operating in Mesopotamia. In his "Account of the Medical Arrangements, etc., during the Siege of

Kut-al-Amara" (Dec. 1915 to April, 1916),* Colonel HEHIR, I.M.S. (1917), states, "in the early stage of the siege a recrudescence of beriberi amongst British troops gave rise to some apprehension, *but it then disappeared*; whilst in Indian troops and followers during the latter half of the siege scurvy caused anxiety." From other entries in this vivid and valuable diary, it is seen that the British troops in the garrison received a cereal ration of wheat flour during the first two months of the siege. After February 5th, 1916, from one-third to one-half of this flour was replaced by barley flour and by "atta," the coarsely-milled wheat usual in the Indian sepoy's ration. It is very significant that beriberi should have broken out among the British troops while upon their normal ration of white wheaten flour, and should have cleared up when they were obliged to share in the more coarsely milled (and doubtless germ-containing) grain of their Indian fellow-soldiers. There is no doubt, from the wealth of detail given in Colonel HEHIR'S report, that the British troops were protected from scurvy by the ample rations of meat† (12oz. at first; later, Jan. 22nd, 1916, 8oz.), or horseflesh (1½lbs. March 4th, 1916), served out to them throughout the siege. The Indian soldiers, while protected from beriberi by the nature of their cereal ration, failed, in many cases, to obtain a sufficient supply of anti-scorbutic vitamine, owing to their refusal to eat fresh meat, in spite of the admirable and persuasive manifesto issued by Colonel HEHIR upon the subject.

During the whole operations in Mesopotamia the Indian soldier seems to have been well protected from beriberi. This was to be expected, for, in addition to an unspoilt cereal, he normally gets a generous daily ration of "dhall," consisting of various dry pulses, which, as may be seen from the foregoing work, are also valuable sources of anti-beriberi vitamine. These, however, did not afford protection from scurvy, which was specially prevalent among the Indians, as, for example, in the summer of 1916, when, presumably, great difficulty was experienced in providing fresh fruit and vegetables (*Mesopotamia Report*, X. 42).

* Appendix III. Mesopotamia Commission Report, 1917.

† This meat appears to have been fresh, except possibly between dates of Dec. 30th and January 29th. Fresh meat has some protective power against beriberi, but this is slight compared with that of grain and pulses. It would be of great interest to know whether, during the outbreaks of beriberi among British troops, prior to the siege of Kut (Colonel HEHIR speaks of a "recrudescence" during the siege) the men were receiving tinned or fresh meat.

The deduction to be drawn from all this experience is as follows :—

For the prevention of beriberi it is in the highest degree desirable that the germ (embryo) and the bran of wheat should not be excluded from the flour destined for manufacture of bread and biscuit for troops on active service. This is the more necessary when the troops are separated from fresh food supplies and the rest of the ration consists largely of tinned foods, seeing that these articles are deficient in all vitamins, owing to their previous sterilisation at high temperatures.*

Yeast and Yeast Extract.—Yeast is acknowledged to be a most valuable source of anti-neuritic vitamine. There is not much evidence at present available as to the value of yeast and yeast extracts in the prevention of human beriberi; we have not been able to find any report of such a trial. Ordinary dried yeast is very disagreeable to take, and causes digestive disturbance, but many preparations possess none of these defects. They have the agreeable savoury taste of a meat extract, and are largely used as an ingredient in certain soup cubes on the market. We have examined one of the principal commercial yeast extracts (Yeast extract A, Tables I. and II.), and could detect no loss of the original vitamine of the yeast owing to the method of preparation. Soup squares form at all times a very popular addition to the soldier's ration, and might well be limited to those containing a certain proportion of yeast extract, seeing that pure meat extracts have been found deficient in anti-beriberi vitamine (see Table II.). By such a measure a valuable extra supply of anti-beriberi vitamine could be added to the ration in a convenient and palatable form.

Dried Eggs.—It will be seen from the examination of two commercial samples of desiccated eggs given in Table II., that so valuable an article of diet as the fresh egg can be successfully dried without losing the anti-beriberi properties. Dried eggs may prove too expensive to form any part of the ordinary soldier's or sailor's dietary, but there can be no doubt as to their suitability for inclusion in hospital stores. Intestinal infections form a large part of the medical casualties in armies on active service, especially when operating in hot climates, and, during both the acute

* In packing and transporting whole-meal or germ-containing flour, extra precautions are usually considered necessary to protect from damp, and the advice of experts should be sought upon these points. No possible difficulty could arise in the case of biscuit baked before transport. Certain samples have been specially investigated by us and were found to be entirely satisfactory for the prevention of beriberi.

stage and the convalescence, the diet is usually restricted to tinned milk and invalid foods, all of which may be regarded as vitamine-free. Mention is made below of the possibility that intestinal affections may in some cases prove a predisposing cause of deficiency disease. It is, therefore, highly desirable that all supply of vitamine should not be cut off during such an illness. Fresh eggs, which provide anti-neuritic vitamine and are also well suited for an invalid diet, are seldom obtainable, and we would, therefore, strongly recommend that dried eggs should be freely used as a substitute. Both commercial samples examined by us were found to be very rich in anti-beriberi vitamine, they were soluble and could be taken raw, and, when cooked, they made excellent and very palatable dishes.

PREVENTION OF SCURVY.

It is a platitude that scurvy can be prevented by the inclusion of fresh vegetables and fruit in a dietary. These are frequently impossible to obtain under the conditions of active service. It is, therefore, our intention under this heading to treat only of such substitutes as are convenient for transport, and hence suited to the needs of armies in the field.

Germinated Pulses as a Substitute for Fresh Vegetables.—The most important fact that has emerged from the study of experimental scurvy is the discovery of FÜRST (1912) that the anti-scorbutic vitamine, absent or deficient in the resting seed, makes its appearance in the early stages of germination. In our own experiments with peas and lentils, these were first soaked in water for 24 hours, the temperature ranging from 50° to 60° F; at this stage a small amount of anti-scorbutic vitamine could already be detected. After germination for a further 48 hours, with access of air, the vitamine-content had increased five- to six-fold, and at this stage the germinated material may be considered the equal of fresh vegetables as regards its anti-scorbutic value (see Table IV. above).

It is difficult to imagine any circumstances in which this form of anti-scorbutic food could not be made available. In the dry form, peas, beans, lentils and other pulses contain only 10 to 15 per cent. of water, and are eminently suited for transport. They are commonly included in the active service dietaries of armies, and in the case of Indian troops, as "dhall," form a considerable proportion of the daily ration. The only

change needed is that these pulses should be issued in the unmilled (not husked or split) condition, and should retain the original seed-coat. Then, in case of unavoidable shortage of fresh fruit or vegetables, a substitute could be made immediately available on the spot by germinating the pulses included in the stores.

The whole operation consists of a preliminary soaking, in which the seeds absorb over 100 per cent. of their original weight of water, followed by germination; after this the food should be cooked and eaten as soon as possible. The time taken by the complete operation could be reduced to 36 hours in a hot climate. In Appendix I. below, p. 178, a set of directions is given, which may be found a useful guide for preparing these germinated pulses in the field.

It is very important that the peas, lentils, etc., should be cooked and eaten as soon as possible after germination, and should not be allowed to dry again. In the process of drying, the anti-scorbutic vitamine developing during the germination, will be destroyed. Having regard to the sensitiveness of this vitamine to high temperatures, it is also important that the pulses should not be cooked longer than is necessary to render them soft and palatable. A period not exceeding 1 to 1½ hours should suffice for peas and about half an hour for lentils. No deterioration in flavour can be detected after germination has taken place.

Dry pulses contain a high proportion of anti-beriberi vitamine, and this was found by GRIJNS* (1901) to be lessened in amount as germination takes place.

We found that in the *early* stages of germination an abundant supply of anti-beriberi vitamine was still retained by our peas and lentils. Dramatic cures of pigeons with acute polyneuritis were obtained with moderate doses (5 to 10 grams) of peas and lentils germinated to the stage, shewn in Fig. 6, in which condition we were using them successfully for the prevention of scurvy.

* Captain COOK, whose long voyage (1772-1775) was notable for the continued good health of the sailors, always took with him a large supply of malted barley. He had the greatest belief in the anti-scorbutic value of a freshly made infusion (sweetwort) and served it out to his men in case of need ("Captain Cook's Voyages," *Everyman* Edition, p. 227).

Some Chinese are accustomed to take part of their daily rice in the germinated condition, and this custom has spread to the Malay States (private communication from Brig.-Gen. ANDERSON) and Dutch Indies (GRIJNS, 1901), where "towgay" or germinated pulses are regularly taken. There appears to be no evidence, however, that the anti-scorbutic properties of these foods have been appreciated.

Freshly germinated pulses (or cereals), therefore, occupy a special position among foodstuffs in being richly endowed with both the anti-scurvy and the anti-beriberi vitamine.*

Vegetables.—Among vegetables the onion is marked out as being specially suited to the need of troops, owing to its great resistance to adverse conditions during transport and to the length of time it will remain wholesome. The anti-scorbutic value is comparable with that of fresh cabbage and its flavour gives it more value as a culinary adjunct than is possessed by any other vegetable.

Potatoes were found to be somewhat inferior in anti-scorbutic properties to cabbage, onions, etc. They are more suitable for transport and keep better than most vegetables, and there is no doubt that they have been proved of great value for the prevention of human scurvy. It must be remembered, however, that the amounts consumed are rather large. In one Irish workhouse† the daily ration of potatoes is 3 lbs.; after a careful study of convict diets, Dr. GUY‡ concluded that 14oz. daily would protect from scurvy, the rest of the ration including 1oz. of other fresh vegetable and 4oz. of meat. Outbreaks of scurvy have repeatedly followed failure of the potato harvest in countries where potatoes are a staple article of diet, *e.g.*, Norway in 1904 (HOLST, FRÖLICH, 1912) and Ireland in 1847 (CURRAN). The recent appearance of scurvy in Glasgow§ and Newcastle|| and Manchester is no doubt to be attributed to the great scarcity of potatoes during the last three or four months.

Fresh Meat.—The expressed juices of fresh meat gave disappointing results in the prevention of guinea-pig scurvy, but there is no doubt that human beings can be protected by its regular use. This is one of the cases which suggest that the guinea-pig is much more susceptible to scurvy than is man, an opinion also held by HOLST and FRÖLICH (1912). Many clinicians believe fresh meat juice to be capable of curing infantile scurvy, and in many Arctic expeditions where scurvy has been escaped, fresh meat of various kinds has been the only anti-scorbutic material present in the diet.

* Refers to note on previous page.

† Limavady Union, Co. Derry.

‡ Dr. GUY's evidence, Report of the Lords Commissioners of the Admiralty on the Outbreak of Scurvy in the recent Arctic Expedition. 1877, par. 5323.

§ *Lancet*, July 8th, 1917.

|| HARLAN. *British Medical Journal*. July 14, 1917.

The following incidents are related by JACKSON and HARLEY (1900:— Six Russian priests spent the winter in a hut at Kharborova, Yugor Straits, with a small Russian boy to wait upon them. Their religion would not permit them to eat reindeer or such meat; they subsisted largely on salted fish, and there were no vegetables. In the following May the little Russian boy was found to be the only surviving person in Kharborava; he was subject to no religious restriction and ate reindeer meat during the winter. JACKSON himself, living among the Samoyads in Waigatz, 1893-1894, noted that among those of the population who winter on the island, and get neither vegetables nor lime-juice, but live largely on fresh reindeer meat, scurvy is unknown. Some Samoyads, however, migrate with Russian peasant traders, and spend the winter near the large rivers in north-east Russia where the diet consists largely of salt fish; among these scurvy is prevalent.

There is no doubt, however, that animal tissues are distinctly inferior in anti-scorbutic properties to those of fresh fruit or vegetables, and that a large and regular ration is necessary for safety. This opinion was expressed by many witnesses in the Admiralty Enquiry* upon the outbreak of scurvy in the Arctic Expedition of 1875, and in the older literature many instances occur in which an apparently liberal meat ration did not prevent scurvy. CURRAN (1847) describes three cases admitted to Swift's Hospital, Dublin, in the great Irish epidemic of 1847, where the previous diet had included $\frac{3}{4}$ lb. on five days of the week. Colonel HEHIR†, in a report suggesting needed reforms in the Indians soldiers' diet in Mesopotamia as early as April, 1915, expresses great doubt whether the authorised meat ration of 28oz. weekly is sufficient to prevent scurvy unless more meat is added and the vegetable ration (2oz. potatoes) is increased. If dry weight is taken into account in comparing the anti-scorbutic value of meat and vegetables, 4oz. meat must be regarded as the equivalent of at least 10oz. vegetables. The British troops during the siege of Kut-al-Amara were doubtless protected from scurvy by their meat or horseflesh rations, but these were very abundant (8oz. to 20oz. daily), see above, p. 165.

Milk.—Fresh cow's milk was found to possess very low anti-scorbutic

* "Report of the Lords Commissioners of the Admiralty upon the Outbreak of Scurvy in the Recent Arctic Expedition." London, 1877.

† Mesopotamia Report, 1917. X. 41.

value in feeding guinea-pigs; satisfactory protection from scurvy was only attained by a large ration, about 100 c.c. daily. It is probable that infants living upon cow's milk do not receive any great excess of vitamine. As regards adults, CURRAN (1847) instances upwards of 80 cases admitted to the Dublin Union Hospitals in the Irish epidemic of 1847; all had been inmates of the union for at least six months previously, and the diet, though deficient in vegetables and meat, had included at least one pint of milk daily.

We have, nevertheless, been much impressed with the great value of milk, even when heated to 120° C. for one hour to destroy the vitamins, as an adjunct to diet. The general condition of animals who received a minimum amount of anti-scorbutic material could be enormously improved by the addition of a daily ration of this heated milk, although the scurvy was not influenced. Therefore, while admitting that milk is of little importance for the prevention of scurvy (or beriberi), its inclusion in a diet, even when tinned and sterilised, would appear to be a very valuable measure.

Fruit.—Fresh fruit juices appear to be among the most valuable anti-scorbutic materials we possess. In our experimental work fresh orange and lemon juices were found very potent. There is also abundant evidence, dating as far back as the beginning of the seventeenth century,* of their value in the prevention of human scurvy. In 1795, largely due to the efforts of Sir GILBERT BLANE (1785, 1830), a regular issue of lemon juice† was ordered in the Navy, and a remarkable decrease of the death-rate was the result. BUDD (1840) states that, whereas 1,457 cases of scurvy were admitted to the Royal Naval Hospital at Haslar in the year 1780, no case was reported in the years 1803 to 1810.

The juice of limes has also been widely esteemed in the past as an anti-scorbutic. There is not, however, much trustworthy evidence as to the anti-scorbutic value of lime-juice when preserved according to modern methods. We have so far found it disappointing for the prevention or cure of guinea-pig scurvy. HOLST and FRÖLICH (1912, p. 96) on the other hand, demonstrated distinct anti-scorbutic properties in two commercial samples of lime-juice, purchased in retail shops in Christiania. The subject is one of very great importance, and we are at present

* JAMES LIND. "A Treatise on Scurvy," 2nd Ed. London, 1757.

† In 1840, the daily ration of lemon juice was 1oz. and 1½oz. sugar, issued two weeks after leaving land. (BUDD, 1840).

engaged on a further investigation, with special reference to the processes of preservation. In the meantime we are not able to express any definite opinion. One thing, however, seems very clear. There is no reason at all why preserved lime-juice should be regarded as a specially concentrated form of anti-scorbutic. This has seemed to be the view generally held, if one may judge by the small size of the ration issued. If lime-juice is issued at all as an anti-scorbutic the ration should be a liberal one—at least 1oz. daily.

IV. RELATION BETWEEN BERIBERI AND SCURVY AS REGARDS TIME OF ONSET, ETC.

It is evident that a diet defective in both classes of vitamines will occasion both beriberi and scurvy, but it is likely that beriberi will precede scurvy in point of time. In "ship" beriberi the symptoms are reminiscent of scurvy, and it is probable that there has been in the diet a deficiency both of anti-beriberi and anti-scurvy vitamines. The "period of resistance," or "period of development," will depend on the degree of deficiency and upon the idiosyncrasy of the individual, but, on the whole, seems to be shorter in case of beriberi. There is good evidence upon this point in the observations of FRASER and STANTON (1909) who found beriberi developing among Javanese coolies after about 80 to 90 days upon a diet composed largely of polished rice. In case of scurvy, the time seems to be longer. Colonel HEHIR* considers four months to be the minimum time in which scurvy will appear in Indian troops on active service, and HOLST and FRÖLICH (1912) refer to two instances in which the time was longer. The first is that of a fanatical vegetarian who wished to prove to the world that human life could be sustained upon a diet of bread and water. The bread was presumably rye bread, and the individual therefore well supplied with anti-beriberi vitamines; he developed scurvy in 7½ months. The second was related by a political refugee in Norway, and deals with the case of 1,400 prisoners in a Russian convict prison. The diet consisted of tea, coarse bread and cabbage soup; the preparation of the latter was so unclean and disgusting that twenty of the prisoners, who were of gentler birth than the others, could not endure to take it. After about six months these twenty shewed symptoms of scurvy, while no case occurred among the rest of the prisoners who took the soup. This incident also shews that, even

* Mesopotamia Report, 1917, X., 41.

after a prolonged boiling, enough anti-scorbutic vitamines remained undestroyed in the cabbage leaves to protect from scurvy.

It is not improbable that the times of onset of these two deficiency diseases might be much shortened in case of any intestinal infection occurring during the "period of development." Such a disease might well impose a drain upon the metabolism which would involve the reserve of vitamins as well as the other resources. It is interesting in this connection to note that among twenty-six cases of beriberi diagnosed in our troops in the Dardanelles in the autumn of 1915, and noted by WILLCOX (1916), eighteen had suffered from diseases of the digestive and alimentary system, previous to the beriberi. At the same time it is possible that the first illness may only indirectly have predisposed to the beriberi by making it necessary to further restrict the already limited diet to such vitamin-free articles as tinned and sterilised milk, etc.

The following case (for details of which I am indebted to Dr. FRANK SAVERY, of Ealing) of a little girl, aged two, who acquired scurvy while suffering from chronic colitis is also to the point. Cow's milk could not be taken and the child was nourished on a brand of dried milk, with the addition of raw meat-juice to her diet as an anti-scorbutic. After some months on this diet, scurvy was diagnosed, but was readily cured by fresh orange juice. Fresh meat-juice has been considered by many clinicians an adequate anti-scorbutic for infants upon a diet of sterilised milk, and is also much esteemed as a cure for infantile scurvy. This incident suggests that the colitis rendered the child more susceptible to scurvy than a normal infant, and also points to the great anti-scorbutic potency of fresh orange juice in comparison with meat-juice.

SUMMARY.

1. To maintain a human being in a satisfactory state of nutrition the diet must contain—

(a) A suitably proportioned supply of protein, fat, carbohydrate, salts and water, and

(b) An adequate amount of accessory food factors, or vitamins. .

Both (a) and (b) are required; excess of one cannot make good any deficiency in the other.

2. These necessary vitamins are, at least, of two kinds: firstly, the anti-neuritic or anti-beriberi vitamin, deficiency of which in a diet occa-

sions beriberi; and, secondly, the anti-scorbutic vitamine, deficiency of which occasions scurvy.

3. Neither of these vitamins has yet been isolated in a pure state, and, for the moment, their presence can only be detected by biological methods.

4. These two classes of vitamins have each their individual rôle in metabolism; they possess properties different from each other and are differently distributed among natural foodstuffs.

5. The distribution of the anti-beriberi vitamine has been investigated by study of experimental polyneuritis in birds, which is generally accepted as analogous to human beriberi. Pigeons, if deprived of anti-beriberi vitamine (*e.g.*, on an exclusive diet of polished rice or white flour, etc.), develop acute polyneuritis (beriberi) in fifteen to twenty-five days. The presence and relative amount of the anti-neuritic vitamine contained in various foodstuffs has been determined by means of curative experiments, and by preventive trials with specially selected diets. In this work we have extended the observations of COOPER (1913-14), and have, in general, followed his methods.

6. The anti-beriberi or anti-neuritic vitamine was found in almost every natural foodstuff examined. The principal source is in the seeds of plants, *e.g.*, cereals and pulses. The most important result emerging from the present work is the fact that *in cereals the anti-beriberi vitamine is mainly deposited in the germ or embryo of the grain, and to a less extent in the bran.* White wheaten flour or polished rice, which consist of the *endosperm* (minus *aleurone layer*) of the grain are deficient in this vitamine, and if employed as sole diet will occasion polyneuritis in pigeons or beriberi in man.

Other important sources of anti-neuritic vitamine are the eggs of animals (*e.g.*, hens' eggs or fish roe) and yeast or yeast extract. Milk and cheese gave disappointing results (COOPER, 1914).

7. From the abundant presence of the anti-beriberi vitamine in dry foodstuffs it is clear that this substance is resistant to drying. It can also withstand exposure to temperatures in the neighbourhood of 100° C. for two hours without significant loss; if heated under pressure to, or near, 120° C. destruction takes place more rapidly (see Table V.).

8. The distribution of the anti-scorbutic vitamine has been investigated by a study of experimental scurvy in guinea-pigs. We have

followed the methods of HOLST and his co-workers (1912) with some modifications. A diet of cereals with water or sterilised milk will cause death from acute scurvy in these animals within a month. The influence of various foodstuffs in preventing scurvy when added to this "scurvy diet" has indicated where the principal sources of the anti-scorbutic vitamine are to be found.

9. The anti-scorbutic vitamine is present in active living vegetable tissues. It is also present in animal tissue, to a much less degree. Fresh vegetables and fresh fruit juices are the most valuable sources of anti-scorbutic vitamine that we possess. All the dried foodstuffs examined, including desiccated vegetables, were more or less deficient in this vitamine.

10. Dry pulses (or cereals) though rich in anti-beriberi vitamine are deficient in anti-scorbutic vitamine, and afford no protection against scurvy. If these are moistened, however, and allowed to germinate, the anti-scorbutic principle is regenerated with the beginnings of active cell life.

Germinated pulses are recommended as a valuable and convenient means of preventing scurvy in the absence of fresh fruit and vegetables. In the dry stage they are eminently suitable for transport and can be moistened and germinated on the spot as required. In Appendix I. is given a method for preparing germinated lentils or peas under active conditions.

11. It is evident from 9 and 10 that the anti-scorbutic vitamine is extremely sensitive to drying. As regards exposure to high temperatures, it is also more unstable than the anti-beriberi vitamine. HOLST (1912) found that the anti-scorbutic power of fresh cabbage was slightly lessened after exposure to 100° C. for half an hour, but that the deterioration was appreciable after one hour; at 110-120° C. the destruction was rapid and complete.

12. It follows from 7 and 11 that neither the anti-neuritic vitamine nor the anti-scorbutic vitamine may be expected to survive in tinned or sterilised foods, considering the high temperature to which these have been subjected in course of preparation.

13. In case of armies or other populations subsisting largely on tinned food, it is imperative to provide adequate supply of vitamine from outside sources.

To prevent beriberi, the bread or biscuit should be made from whole-meal or germ-containing flour.

To prevent scurvy, if a supply of fresh fruit or vegetables is not procurable, germinated pulses should be added to the diet.

In conclusion, our best thanks are due to the following firms for generous help in the supply of material for our investigations to:— Messrs. Steele & Co., rice millers; Messrs. Brown & Polson, maize millers; The Hovis-Bread Flour Co. and Messrs. J. & H. Robinson, wheat millers, and especially to Mr. E. G. Ellis, of the last-named firm for much kind help, information and advice; Messrs. L. Rose & Co., for samples of specially prepared lime-juice; Elizabeth Lazenby & Son, Harrod's Stores, and Messrs. Crosse & Blackwell. We also wish to express our thanks to Professor HARDEN, F.R.S., for preparing some of the extracts mentioned in Table II.; to Miss MABEL RHODES, for kindly making the drawings from which figures 1 to 6 are made; and lastly to our assistant, Mr. A. H. ROBINS, for his devoted care and feeding of the experimental birds in the beriberi enquiry.

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APPENDIX I.

SUGGESTED METHOD OF USING PEAS, LENTILS, OR OTHER PULSES (DHALL) FOR THE PREVENTION OF SCURVY, IN THE ABSENCE OF FRESH VEGETABLES.

1. The dry seeds must be whole, retaining the original seed-coat, not milled or decorticated. See Fig. 5 (a) peas and (b) lentils.

2. They must be soaked in water for several hours; the time necessary depends on the temperature, 24 hours at 50° to 60° F. and 12 hours or less at 90° F.

3. The water must then be drained away and the peas, etc., allowed to remain in the moist condition with access of air. They will then germinate and the small rootlet grow out as in Fig. 6 (a) peas and (b) lentils. This germination will take 48 hours at 50° to 60° F. and 12 to 24 hours at 80° F.

4. The operations described in 2 and 3 could conveniently be done under active service conditions in such manner as the following:—

Soaking.—The peas or other pulses, placed in a *clean* sack, should be steeped in a trough, barrel, or other suitable vessel, full of clean water, and should be occasionally stirred. The sack and trough, etc., should be large enough to allow for the swelling of the peas to about three times their original size. In a hot climate 6 to 12 hours should suffice for this soaking.

Germination.—The peas should be lifted out of the water and spread out to a *depth not exceeding 2 to 3 inches* in a trough or other vessel with sides and bottom porous or well perforated with holes. This is to allow *complete* access of air. *The seeds must be kept in a moist atmosphere.* This is done by covering with damp cloth or sacking, which is sprinkled (by hand or automatically) as often as is required to keep the peas thoroughly moist underneath. The germination should reach the stage shewn in Fig. 6 within 24 hours in a hot climate. *All the vessels should be clean.*

5. *It is important that the germinated pulses should be cooked and eaten as soon as possible after germination, and should not be allowed to become dry again; in that case the anti-scorbutic properties, acquired during the process of germination, will again be destroyed. The pulses should not be cooked longer than necessary.*

LISTER INSTITUTE,

June 15th, 1917.

Professor A. E. BOYCOTT: All I have to say is to draw the attention of the meeting to three microscopical specimens which are under the microscopes. Through the kindness of Miss CHICK, I have had the opportunity of examining a number of animals dead of this disease. I express no opinion as to whether it is the same condition as human scurvy, but the specimens in the room illustrate what is the only considerable anatomical change which one finds in these animals, namely, the disorder there is at the growing ends of bones. That is the lesion to which HOLST drew particular attention, and he used it as a diagnostic test as to whether an animal had experimental scurvy or not. It is always present in the guinea-pigs, and it consists of a number of complicated details, which are best appreciated by looking at the specimens. But, roughly, what happens, as far as we can make out, is that the preparatory changes in the cartilage, before it is turned into bone, do not come off, or if they do, they occur in some irregular way which obstructs the connective tissue, and prevents it performing its ordinary function. The result is, that at the growing ends of bones—and it is particularly well seen at the junction of the bony to the cartilaginous parts of the ribs—instead of there being an orderly conversion of cartilage into bone, there is disorder. The end of the medullary cavity, instead of being active tissue, forming periosteal bone and being filled with bone-marrow, is filled up with a lot of connective tissue which does not go on to the formation of bone. That wad of connective tissue is what gives the gross appearance to which HOLST draws attention particularly: that at the ends of these bones there is a clear area.

With regard to the rest of the organs of these animals, it is curious to note the extraordinarily little change one finds. The animals are very thin, wasted, etc.; but we have examined in a series of animals the various organs of the body without finding any change of any importance. There is no question that these changes in the bones are not what causes death; they are the dramatic and obvious anatomical peculiarity.

Under the microscopes there are two sections of the ribs of scurvy animals, and, for comparison, there is a section from a normal guinea-pig.

Sir PATRICK MANSON: I would like to congratulate the Society upon having received a lecture of so interesting a character. I have

seen a good deal of beriberi, from a clinical point of view, and I recognise that, in certain instances, the multiple peripheral neuritis which we call beriberi is the result of a deficiency in the matter of feeding. But I have a strong suspicion that that is not the explanation of all of those cases which we call beriberi. I remember very well a case of what looked like ordinary beriberi which developed in hospital; the patient died. I called it "beriberi;" it had all the signs of multiple peripheral neuritis, such as we usually mean by that word. After that patient's body had been removed, a patient suffering from stone in the bladder occupied the same bed. He developed the same kind of condition and died. I had crushed the stone, and the patient seemed to be doing well, but he developed multiple peripheral neuritis of the beriberi type and died. A very few days after that, a patient who had Potts' disease of the spine, occupied the same bed, and within a day or two, this patient also got multiple peripheral neuritis; and within a day or two on either side similar cases also occurred. This strongly suggested to my mind that beriberi might be really an infectious disease, one which was transferable from one patient to another. Early impressions are strong, and this experience I have not forgotten. We are apt to be too much fascinated by a new theory in pathology, or even by words or phrases. There is a difficulty in explaining some disease; then some new pathological fashion turns up, and we are apt to say that it applies to the unexplained disease. Thus I fear that the term "deficiency disease" is prone to obsess our judgment in these cases of endemic or epidemic multiple peripheral neuritis. I have no doubt that a large number of cases of what we call "beriberi" are really etiologically different diseases. In epidemics among coolies in tin mines and in plantations, where the food is bad, badly-cooked rice, or over-milled rice, I think the disease is a deficiency disease. But I am convinced that there are other forms of epidemic multiple peripheral neuritis which have not received enough attention. I look upon the term "beriberi" as a word which refers to a group of symptoms, not to one pathological entity merely. I remember very well, some years ago, at the Seamen's Hospital, a patient came in with the usual signs of beriberi. There were plenty of beriberi cases in the wards at the time. He had difficulty in walking, œdema, palpitations, and all the usual signs of beriberi. On examining his blood, we found the malaria parasite. We gave him

quinine, and all the symptoms cleared up rapidly. I think that something similar must occur in many other infections.

I would like to ask the authors if experiments have been done by them with boiled rice in the case of pigeons, fowls, and guinea-pigs, and if so, what was the result?

Lieut.-Colonel J. C. MARTIN, F.R.S. : I was delighted to hear what Sir PATRICK MANSON said about Dr. CHICK'S account which we have just listened to, which seemed to me to be a model of exposition, and one suited to this time of day.

I have seen a good many hundreds of nutritional experiments, and, amongst them, the latter part of this research which Miss CHICK and Miss HUME have been conducting. And, first of all, I would emphasise the enormous amount of work which is involved in this kind of study. The chemist, to test the result of his experiments, puts a piece of litmus paper or other indicator in and gets his answer straight off; but here the answer to every question asked involves one or two months' careful watching and feeding of the animals. The result of one series of experiments must emerge before you know how to go on to the next step. Of all the nutritional experiments I have seen, these are, far and away, the best. The one thing which is fatal to nutritional work is, to send the animals away to an animal-house to be looked after by somebody else, and the great feature of this present work is, that these animals have been tended and nursed and fed by the observers themselves. It has always been known that they did actually take their ration, both their main ration, and the particular substance the effect of which it was hoped to ascertain.

Recently, there has, I understand, been a magnificent experiment on deficiency diseases made upon the garrison of Kut. Both beriberi and scurvy occurred amongst the garrison, the former in Europeans, the latter in Indians. As far as I know they did not overlap. The diets of the two kinds of troops were different. The Europeans had fresh horse-flesh and white bread and white flour. The natives had lentils and a certain amount of wholemeal flour, as, with the exception of the Ghurka regiments, they would not eat fresh horse. Those who had the fresh meat were saved from scurvy; whereas the native who would not eat the horse got scurvy. The native did not get beriberi because the

bulk of his diet consisted of pulses and coarsely ground attar. (wheat).

The question of the exact pathology of the disease produced in the guinea-pig by depriving it of green food is interesting. HOLST'S results have been criticised on the grounds that the disease is not true scurvy. To my mind, it does not matter a bit whether it is so or not. The pathological condition, whatever its precise nature, is caused by depriving the animal of green stuff. I think that it closely resembles scurvy, not so much scurvy as seen in the adult, but rather more that of the baby, and it must be remembered that the animals used for this research were growing guinea-pigs. In adult scurvy the characteristic feature is the extraordinary tendency to hæmorrhages, and in older guinea-pigs deprived of green stuffs hæmorrhages are even more extensive.

Sir PATRICK MANSON asked Miss CHICK the question, whether the same polyneuritis was produced if the rice were cooked? I should be sorry to deprive her of the pleasure of answering it, but I am wondering whether she will remember that the discovery by EIJKMAN in 1897, that deficiency in diet was a cause of polyneuritis was actually made with boiled rice. EIJKMAN was the pathologist at a hospital in Java. For purposes of economy, the fowls were fed upon the rice that the patients left, and suffered from a curious disease, with paralysis, from which they died. EIJKMAN was led to enquire into the causation of this calamity to the fowls and found therein the interpretation of beriberi.

Mr. JAMES CANTLIE: In reference to what Sir PATRICK MANSON has said, I beg to state that my first introduction to beriberi was in Hong Kong, when taking charge of Sir PATRICK MANSON'S ward while he was on holiday. There were in the ward a number of surgical and a number of medical cases—two of them with beriberi. When Sir PATRICK returned, I pointed out to him that every man (six) in the ward who had an open sore or wound had contracted beriberi during his absence, while those men who suffered from ailments, with no sore or wound escaped infection. I became impressed at that time with the idea that beriberi was an infectious disease, inasmuch as six cases in that ward had evidently become infected after admission by the beriberi cases already in the ward. It is very difficult to get rid of an early impression of this nature, and with that experience before me I have always found it difficult to

subscribe whole-heartedly to the conclusion that beriberi is to be ascribed exclusively to aberrations in diet. I thought it worth while mentioning this fact in view of what Sir PATRICK MANSON has just said, as any observation by him always deserves the closest attention.

Lieut.-Colonel COPEMAN, M.D., F.R.S.: I would like to associate myself with what Sir PATRICK MANSON has said in returning thanks to Miss CHICK and Miss HUME for this very interesting investigation, in which I am especially interested, because being at present in charge of the Hygiene Department of the Royal Army Medical College, I have seen a good deal of the work in the course of its progress, and have, as a matter of fact, supplied some of the material, including Army lime-juice, which, apparently, was found to be absolutely useless for the particular purpose of scurvy prevention. Much of this work, as Miss CHICK said, has been done for the Army Medical Department, with the view of finding, in the first instance, some material which, while useful in the prophylaxis and treatment of beriberi, could be easily transported and would not readily undergo change under tropical conditions. I do not know whether Colonel MARTIN saw the "savoury tablets" we sent out before he came back. Miss CHICK tested them and found them useful in curing the polyneuritis of pigeons; some thousands of pounds have been sent out, but we have yet to learn what has been the result of their use on the human subject. They consist mainly of marmite, with a basis of pea-flour cooked in bacon-fat, to improve the flavour and to obviate the bitter taste which raw pea-flour possesses. I have recently heard from my colleague, Dr. BUCHANAN, in Mesopotamia, that beriberi is not so prevalent as formerly, but I would not like to say it is in consequence of the use of this material which has been sent out. Yeast is one of the best antidotes for the polyneuritis of pigeons, but even pressed yeast does not keep at a high temperature, especially in the presence of moisture. The tablets of which I speak have the advantage of not undergoing change in their appearance, their consistency, or their curative effect, after some considerable time, and after exposure to such temperatures as are experienced in the tropics.

With regard to the use of lime-juice in scurvy, I suppose some difference in value as an anti-scorbutic may be due to the fact that apparently the lime-juice manufactured now is sterilised or preserved

to a greater extent than previously. I do not know whether its diminished efficiency is due to added alcohol, or to the heat used in sterilising, unfavourably affecting the vitamins. But since Miss CHICK has demonstrated the fact that germinating peas contain anti-scurvy vitamins, these can be carried about in the dry condition, and one can subsequently cause them to germinate whenever and wherever you may want to use them.

The guinea-pig exhibited seems, so far as I know, to be in the condition described by Colonel MARTIN; the pathological condition being very similar to that seen in the scurvy of infants. But I agree with him it does not much matter what the precise condition is, so long as one gets the index required for experimental purposes.

I am very glad to have had the opportunity of hearing this lecture and seeing the demonstrations.

Fleet-Surgeon P. W. BASSETT-SMITH, R.N.: Lime-juice as supplied to Navy undoubtedly was useful in preventing scurvy. That lime-juice comes from the West Indies; it has a good body, is sweet, and differs from that so often supplied at the present time. Perhaps it is the superiority of the West Indian lime-juice which gives it its curative powers.

Dr. G. C. Low: I would like to say a few words on another branch of the subject, which has not been much touched upon in the paper, namely, the clinical aspect of beriberi. Large numbers of cases of this disease are constantly passing through the Royal Albert Dock Hospital, London School of Tropical Medicine, and since the question of vitamins has come prominently to the front we have been trying foods specially rich in these substances for curative purposes. We do not, however, find that the cases respond in the same marvellous manner as pigeons, and, as a matter of fact, it is rather difficult to be certain that they get better more quickly on those foods as compared with ordinary diet. Yeast has been tried, but here again the results are no better than before. It seems that in man the nerves take much longer to regenerate, and the changes produced are sometimes so extreme that the patient may lie ill for months irrespective of what sort of food is given him. I recollect one case who was shewing no signs of improvement, and he was given potato

skins with remarkable results; from that day he went steadily on and convalesced in a satisfactory manner. It was supposed that the vitamins in the skin were responsible, but after hearing Miss CHICK's paper this is not so clear, as I notice she says there are practically no vitamins in potatoes. It is possible, of course, as Sir PATRICK MANSON suggests, that all cases of multiple peripheral neuritis are not beriberi in the strictest sense, and other causes may be responsible. One could hardly expect vitamins to do much good in such cases. There is a large field open for further experimental work in the treatment of human cases of beriberi. Vitamins, I admit, will prevent such cases, but, once having occurred, what part do these substances play in accelerating the return of the nerves to normal?

The CHAIRMAN: Dr. LOW has just told us the remarkable effect of feeding a beriberi patient on potato skins, and would have us believe that it was due to the vitamins contained in them. But from my experience of military hospitals—and I am sure Fleet-Surgeon BASSETT-SMITH will bear me out—if we fed our men on potato skins we would almost empty our hospitals within twenty-four hours, whatever disease our patients were nominally suffering from.

You will agree with me that we have listened to a most interesting, instructive and important paper by Miss CHICK. What can be more important for a nation than its food? It is a subject which should receive much more attention than it does.

Miss H. CHICK: I think there is little to say in reply. It is not all pigeons which get cured so quickly. If you do not treat a case at the right moment, but let it go on, or give an insufficient amount to cure, so that there is a relapse in a few days, the disease may become chronic, and then the bird may take a month or six weeks to cure. And it must be remembered that all processes in the pigeon go on very quickly compared with the rate in the human. A patient who has had beriberi for some time, so that it has become chronic, will naturally take some time to cure. But in the case of ordinary acute epidemic beriberi, the cures are pretty quick when the right sort of diet is provided on the spot.

Dr. G. C. Low: The patients get it coming home on the ships. Many of our cases are quite acute; I was not speaking of old chronic cases.

Miss H. CHICK: I should like to know what would happen if one gave a diet with wheat germ in it to such cases, because we found in chronic pigeon cases which would not get better, that an occasional big meal of wheat germ improved them. Has anything like that been tried?

Dr. G. C. Low: No; but I shall be glad to try it in the next cases we have.